

Online Experiential Learning: Challenges and Experiences in the Laboratory School

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Abstract:- Pre-service teachers will be the next teachers to hone, mold, and shape that will instill knowledge to the minds, hearts, and abilities of learners. So it is critical to assist these pre-service teachers, by understanding their challenges and how we can help them going to succeed. The purpose of this research was to find out and discuss the experiences and challenges faced encountered by pre-service teachers of Leyte Normal University at the Laboratory School. Furthermore, this also determined on how pre-service teachers adjust from the challenges to succeed Experiential Learning Courses and what probable strategies that can be applied to address such difficulties. This study utilized a Hermeneutic Phenomenology as research design because the study is focused on subjective experience of individuals or groups. A purposive sampling method was used for the selection of participants, an interview guide was used in a one-on-one online interview, and the data gathered was carefully analyzed through thematic analysis. The study found that the experience of pre-service teachers was gave them a lot of opportunity in improving their skills and knowledge as a future educator. It is also found that the challenges of pre-service teachers during online experiential learning in the laboratory school are: Lack of skills in technology, lack of communication, and not participative students. Subsequently, pre-service have different ways in adjusting from the challenges they faced, their attitude and behavior and by being flexible and resourceful.

Keywords:- *Experiential learning; Pre-service teachers, Challenges, Experiences*

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

Humans are the only living entities that have fundamental adaptive expertise in the learning process. The learning species and survival depends on the ability to adapt not only in the reactive sense of fitting into the physical and social worlds, rather in the proactive sense of creating and shaping one's individual (Kolb,1984). Incorporating real world experiences into academic study is pivotal for it holds in improving the substance of knowledge and skills of a student as they play as a primary agent of learning. In the context of education, various learning approaches is being introduce to achieve the needs of every learners, and one of which is experiential learning. As defined by Salandanan (2010), experiential learning is a way of acquiring knowledge

or skills through direct experience. It is referred to as learning through experience, and learning through discovery and exploration. It is either learning by yourself or experiential learning through programs structured by others (Smith, 2012).

CHED Memorandum Order No. 30 (CMO 30) was in place for the goal of standardizing undergraduate teacher education in the country in order to stay up with global competitiveness demands. Also, it sets a design that emphasizes in linking of foundational, theoretical, methodological and experiential knowledge in the various learning experiences in the curriculum. The experiential learning in the curriculum consist of Field Study (FS) courses and Practice Teaching course that intended to the pre-service teachers to equip and honed their knowledge in the context of education. Article V. sec.13 of CHED Memorandum Order no. 30 states that, "field study courses are intended to provide students with practical learning experiences in which they observe, verify, reflect-on, in actual school settings. The experiences will begin with field observation and gradually intensify until students undertake practice teaching. FS course will engage a pre-service teacher in an actual classroom setting and learning environment, in which they need to have a direct observation of teaching learning events focusing on the implementation of educational ideas taught in content and pedagogy courses. It allows pre-service teachers to participate and help in a practical teaching-learning activities related to assessment of learning, production of instructional materials, and other classroom routines.

Practice Teaching course on the other hand, is the next course to pursue after Field Study course, it is essential for completing professional training. It is also included in teacher education courses that provides real experience in many tasks of a teacher, such as in teaching and building subject mastery to students. Globally, the teaching internship has been cited as the most significant, exciting, and difficult experience teacher trainees encounter throughout their entire teacher preparation program. It is believed that personal experience is the best way to learn skills in any job or profession, most specially teaching. With that, education internship is designed to provide students with the opportunity to engage themselves in the classroom teaching experience. It is also the concluding experience for a student taking up education program. Furthermore, according to Otara (2014), internship is considered as a comprehensive classroom experience that helps pre-service teachers to acquire and polish the skills, competencies that required to be an effective educator in any academic institutions. Along with

that, student teachers/interns collaborate with professional mentor teachers and teaching internship supervisor to develop into more reflective professional skills that create environments, organize content knowledge, and teach in ways that encourage student learning.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in the Philippines requires pre-service teachers to complete direct teaching as a concluding stage after Field Study course in which they experience teaching in actual classrooms. To ensure quality education throughout the country, the CHED and the Department of Education (DepEd) issued Joint Memorandum Order No. 39 of 2005, outlining standards for the deployment of student teachers (Department of Education, 2005). Managing classrooms, lesson planning, and assessing students are just a few of the everyday tasks of a teaching intern. These experiences prompt Practice Teachers to reflect on their immediate future career and professional growth. And this nurtures the development of PTs belief and teacher identity as they acquire a more in-depth understanding of an actual classroom environment (Ugalingan et. al., 2021).

However, when COVID-19 spread out in the Philippines, community quarantines and lockdowns were carried out by the government that forced academic institution in particular, to get used in the “new normal”. Due to this, CMO No. 04 Series of 2020 was implemented that adopts the guidelines for on the implementation of Flexible Learning to the private and public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). In other words, the dynamics of teaching and learning need to be re-conceptualized since face-to-face interaction is not possible. As a result, all the usual face-to-face school-related activities that involves students were resorted to different learning modalities which are modular and online learning, including the conduct of Field Study course and Teaching Internship course of pre-service teachers as joint memorandum of Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and Department of Education (DepEd) issued the New Normal Policies and Guidelines on the Deployment of Pre-Service Teachers for Field Study and Teaching Internship for AY 2020-2001. Pre-service teachers are being deployed to the laboratory schools to have experiential learning course, and everything they do is being hold virtually through Google meet or Zoom application, from orientations, teaching demonstrations, class observation and the proper teaching session to their assigned class.

Furthermore, there are a huge difference in dealing with the conditions brought about by the pandemic today. This drastic change carried challenges considering that experiential learning courses are expected to give students a chance to immerse themselves in the actual classroom experience. Also, it concerns to the increasing trend towards a progressive educational system that emphasized the need for quality teachers for effective learning. The experiences and challenges of pre-service teachers will give them a hard time when they are already in their profession of teaching, considering the learning environment in an actual classroom is different from virtual. With the aforesaid propositions, the researchers are driven to unfold the experiences and challenges faced by the pre-service teachers who encountered online experiential

learning courses. The researchers believed that there is a need to know the experiences and challenges encountered by the pre-service teacher in their online experiential learning, knowing real-world learning is a critical aspect of teacher education and frequently described field study and internship as the highlight of their four years of college.

B. Statement of the Problem

This study will be utilizing Hermeneutical phenomenology to produce a rich-textual descriptions and interpretations to the experiences and challenges encountered by the pre-service teachers in their online experiential learning courses in the laboratory school.

Specifically, the researchers seek to answer the following:

- What challenges experienced by the pre-service teachers in their online experiential learning courses in the laboratory school?
- What adjustments they made in such challenges to complete online experiential learning courses?

C. Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored to Experiential Learning Theory of David Kolb and Sociocultural Theory of Lev Vygotsky.

Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) works in four stages—(1) having a concrete experience followed by (2) observation and reflection on that experience which leads to (3) the formation of abstract concepts (analysis) and generalizations (conclusions) which are then (4) used to test hypothesis in future situations, resulting in new experiences which means that learning is an integrated process where a new experience is reflected upon where one may discover any inconsistencies between experience and understanding. The first two stages of the cycle involve grasping an experience, the second two focus on transforming an experience (Western Governors University, 2020). This supports to the idea that the best way to student skills in any profession, especially teaching, is through personal experience. In which it parallel the concept of ELT that there would be a concrete learning when a learner gets experience, and interprets that experience in a new way. Furthermore, according to Otara (2014), experiential learning is considered as a comprehensive classroom experience that helps pre-service teachers to acquire and polish the skills, competencies that required to be an effective educator in any academic institutions. Along with that, pre-service teachers collaborate with professional mentor teachers and supervisor to develop into a more reflective professional skills that create environments, organize content knowledge, and teach in ways that encourage student learning.

On the other hand, In Sociocultural theory believes that social interaction is the key to cognitive development. Vygotsky believes that intellectual abilities are guided through the interaction of more knowledgeable others and the learner because he believes that without their guidance, the learner would not be able to advance because his or her knowledge would only be based on his or her discoveries. One of the most known concepts of this theory is the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) where students are cognitively prepared

but still need the guidance of more knowledgeable others to learn. It is in this zone where the more knowledgeable others help develop the learners' skill but withdraw when the learners can already do it on their own. In this theory, teacher interns play a crucial role in the learners' Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) so it is necessary to recognize the challenges of pre-service teachers for they are in the stage where their skills and knowledge are being developed all throughout their journey in teaching profession. Hence, about the study it is important to focus on experiential learning on learning outcomes. To focus on online tool development on learning outcomes, Kearney and colleagues (2012) created a pedagogical framework that consists of three features: personalization, authenticity and collaboration. Personalization implies that ownership, agency and autonomous learning are important aspects when designing online tools. Authenticity highlights the opportunities for contextualized, situated learning. Collaboration captures the connected aspects of online tools. Use of time and space are central elements of the pedagogical framework. Online tools offer opportunities to learn in a variety of "spaces," using virtual environments, which makes learning time and place independent (Kearney et al, 2012).

D. Significance of the Study

The researchers believed that this study will be beneficial to the following:

- **Future Field Study 1 & 2, and Teaching Internship course students.** This study will help them prepare to the challenges will be facing in online experiential learning courses in Laboratory school.
- **Pre-service teachers.** The findings of this study will give them awareness with the challenges in online experiential learning courses and will provide them insights what adjustments they need to easily cope the online experiential learning experience.
- **Cooperating Teachers.** The findings of this study will help him/her to have necessary modification and improvement to assist the challenges faced by the students taking experiential learning courses through online. They can also have ways to still assure the quality learning in experiential learning courses in preparing them in the actual field of teaching profession.
- **Future Researchers.** This study will serve as guide to further develop the study and encourage them to deepening or expanding the scope of study in relation to experiential learning courses.

E. Definition of Terms

The following terms will be defined operationally and will be utilized all throughout the study.

- **Experiential Learning** - An approaches in learning courses for undergraduate education students. This includes Field Study and Teaching Internship courses, a year-long engagement that supports authentic experiential learning from field study and actual classroom immersion.

- **Laboratory School** – A school operated in the colleges or universities. It is otherwise known as demonstration school that includes pre-school, elementary, and secondary school.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This chapter contains relevant studies, articles, and other forms of literature in connection to the study.

In the Philippines, three key educational regulatory agencies are in charge of the execution, development, and monitoring of the country's educational programs. The Department of Education (DepEd) is tasked on basic education in both public and private schools. Other two education sectors are the Commission of Higher Education (CHED), which controls both public and private university and graduate education, and the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), which oversees technical-vocational and middle-level education (CHED Historical Background). Similarly, the two departments, CHED and DepEd, collaborate to enhance teacher education in the country. CHED monitors, assesses, and establishes all programs/curriculums, as well as the performance of all higher learning institutions. DepEd, on the other hand, establishes student teaching or teaching internship curriculum rules and policies that are unique to both BSEd and BEEd programs. In other words, DepEd has no direct authority over the teaching curriculum of the Bachelor of Arts program; CHED evaluates it. However, should BA graduates decide to teach in the public schools, they need to take and finish the teaching certificate course which includes 18 units of professional teaching courses; and they should take and pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Furthermore, when these pre-service teachers passed the licensure examination for teachers conducted by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), and would apply to become teachers in the government schools, DepEd screens and determines their qualifications (Ulla, 2016).

Since the start of the Covid-19 pandemic, schools around the world have close down to prevent the further spread of the virus. As a result, the sheer spread and urgency to shift to online learning and material resources readily available to teachers and students (Adedoyin & Sokyan, 2020). Moreover, Kim (2021) observed that the shift to online learning has been driven out of necessity due to the restrictions imposed by the pandemic. In addition, the materials and lessons created because of this shift to online learning have not been crafted to suit maximizing teaching and learning opportunities. Rospigliosi (2020) maintained that the shift to online teaching has accelerated changes in the education sector.

In the case of the experiential learning courses, studies report that this was a very challenging task for teacher education institutions since the internship was not possible (Cho & Clark-Gareca, 2020). While there is a dearth of investigations documenting the internship during the pandemic, there are several of significance in the present investigation. Challenges such as on the experiences of pre-service teachers who are having experiential learning courses

through online, creating teaching and learning opportunities to maximize engagement remain to be a problem.

➤ *Experiential Learning Courses*

According to CHED Memorandum Order no. 11 series of 2009, there are twelve (12) units of experiential learning that comprises of six (6) units of Field Study courses to be taken concurrently with Professional Education courses and six (6) units of practice teaching to be taken after the professional education courses. Field Study Courses are crafted to prepare and equip the pre-service teacher for their In-Campus and Off-Campus Practice-Teaching Performance with the same in practice teaching.

The Experiential Learning Courses (ELC) Handbook authored by the Teacher Education Council of the Department of Education provided ELC framework, the guidelines for Field Study students the course syllabi and a bit of recommended activity sheets for students. The CHED mandates that teacher education students should be equipped with the learning experiences that will meet the standards of the learning environment in Basic Education Schools (BES). Hence, CMO 30. s., 2004 sets forth the one-unit Experiential Learning Courses (ELC) known as Field Study (FS). The ELC are indispensable components of the New Teacher Education Curriculum, per CMO No. 30 s., 2004. This pursuant to National Competency Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS), the core of the Teacher Education Development Program (TEDP) of the government. The ELC’s are intended to provide students with actual learning experiences in which they can observe, verify, reflect on, and practice the different components of teaching-learning process in a variety of authentic school settings. Such experiences, which are built around mentoring, will begin with field observation and will gradually intensify into participation and until students undertake practice teaching (Burac, 2020).

Education is one of the most important tools for human resource problem. The number of educated people and the standard of education are important factors in a country’s growth. In the long run, proper and high –quality education will contribute to poverty eradication, good government leadership, high-quality public health, and a more environmentally-friendly climate. Meanwhile, some reports

say that teacher education is in crisis around the world. This is attributed to several, including the quantity and consistency of applicants entering teacher education, attaining essential competencies, and student-teacher readiness for entry and retention in the profession. . There is also a “theory –practice divide”, which refers to disconnect between the essence of teacher training programs and teachers’ interactions as full-fledged professionals. It was concluded that new teachers are underprepared for the job and have concerns about their professional identity. As for the academic year 2020-2021, the Commission on Higher Education released an unnumbered memorandum on the current normal policies and recommendations for the deployment of pre-service teachers for field study and teaching internship, with all these underlying concepts probing that practice teaching is indeed pivotal in developing more competent teachers. As stipulated in this memorandum, TEIs are enjoined to implement the necessary modifications in the teaching internship and field study delivery given their context and available resources. Field Study and Teaching Internship programs, on the other hand, must be experiential, incorporating a variety of new standard learning modalities, developmental by coaching and mentoring, and consistent with the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) and the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). TEIs and Cooperating Schools shall follow the Student Internship Program provisions in the Philippines, as outlined in CHED. Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 104, series of 2017, as well as the Guidelines on the Required Health Standards in Basic Education Offices and Schools, as outlined in DepEd Order No. 014, series of 2020. This benefits the students’ health, ensures their learning and visibility and ensures their protection while on internship. The challenge now is to know the difficulties that practice teacher face in their teaching practice under the new normal despite the efforts and policies put in place by CHED and by various universities and colleges. The study expands on multiple researches regarding the challenges encountered by practice teachers in different parts of the world.

Joint CHED-DEPED Memorandum for the New Normal Policies and Guidelines on the Deployment of Pre-service teachers for Field Study and Teaching Internship for AY 2020-2021 has mandated a new normal teaching-learning activities that are expected in the experiential learning courses.

Teaching-Learning Activities	Field Study Courses	Teaching Internship
1. Observation of Classes, Pre Observation and Post-Observation Conferences	a. Viewing selected videos of demonstration lessons from YouTube and other sources and reflecting on the teaching-learning activities using guide questions through modules and worksheets b. Viewing videos involving teaching-learning processes in different LDMs focusing on the delivery of the MostEssential Learning Competencies in actual teaching and reflecting on these processes c. Interviewing teachers on lesson preparation in flexible learning and distance learning delivery mode	a. Observing the teaching-learning process in Flexible Learning and in different Distance Learning Delivery Modes (online, radio-based instruction, television-based instruction, and other modalities) focusing on the development of the MELCs and reflecting on these processes b. Attending pre-observation and post-observation conferences with the Cooperating Teacher and the College Supervisor c. Keeping a daily reflection journal.

	<p>d. Attending pre observation and post-observation conferences with the Resource Teacher and the College Supervisor</p> <p>e. Submitting anecdotal reports on details during the observation sessions</p>	
2. Class Routines	<p>a. Being oriented on protocols for classes in the learning modality employed by the school</p> <p>b. Viewing of video-recordings of home-based learning routines</p> <p>c. Submitting anecdotal reports on details during the observation sessions</p>	<p>a. Being oriented on protocols for classes in the learning modality employed by the school</p> <p>b. Assisting the Cooperating Teacher in the preparation and implementation of class guidelines for holding classes through distance learning modalities.</p>
3. Preparation of Instructional Materials	<p>a. Compiling print and non-print materials from open educational resources which are related to the lessons, contextualized to the needs of the students, and aligned with the MELCs</p> <p>b. Accomplishing worksheets related to the development of instructional materials</p>	<p>a. Assisting the Cooperating Teacher in the preparation of presentations and learning materials to be used in classes.</p> <p>b. Developing contextualized instructional materials appropriate for the demonstration teaching modality.</p>
4. Class Activities	<p>a. Documenting and compiling class activities which are related to the lessons, contextualized to the needs of the students, and aligned with the MELCs</p> <p>b. Analyzing how resource teachers effectively use open educational resources including DepEd Commons to deliver the competencies of a specific discipline</p> <p>c. Accomplishing worksheets on observations of class activities</p>	<p>a. Assisting the CTs in preparing class activities</p> <p>b. Facilitating LDM class activities with minimum supervision from the CTs.</p> <p>c. Designing contextualized learning activities aligned with the MELCs.</p>
5. Assessment Practices	<p>a. Compiling various assessment materials used by the resource teachers in the implementation of their LDM</p> <p>b. Accomplishing worksheets on assessment procedures observed.</p>	<p>a. Assisting the Cooperating Teacher to create assessment materials related to the lessons, applicable to various distance learning delivery modes</p> <p>b. Designing templates for various assessment tools with suitable scoring rubrics</p> <p>c. Designing templates for reflection activities on the teaching-learning process</p> <p>d. Assisting the Cooperating Teacher in checking students' outputs</p>
6. Demonstration Teaching	<p>a. Observing PTs in their final demonstration teaching using the LDM of the partner school</p> <p>b. Accomplishing worksheets to reflect on the observed demonstration teaching</p>	<p>a. Preparing lesson plans, study guides, modules, and teaching materials relevant to LDM of the partner school and as required by the Cooperating Teacher.</p> <p>b. Conducting daily and final demonstration teaching using the LDM of the partner school</p>
7. School Forms	<p>a. Familiarization with school forms and how to prepare them</p> <p>b. Accomplish worksheets to practice preparing school forms</p>	<p>a. Assisting the Cooperating Teacher in accomplishing school forms</p>
8. Networking and Linkages	<p>a. Participating in webinars and other online professional activities</p>	<p>a. Assisting the CTs in parent-teacher conferences</p> <p>b. Providing support by being volunteer tutors as part of auxiliary service in partner schools</p>

		c. Participating in local and international webinars and other online professional activities
9. Classroom-Based Action Research	a. Doing professional readings on different CBARs related to the teaching-learning processes b. Preparing reflection papers on the studied CBARs	a. Conducting CBARs on a specific teaching-learning area b. Listing references used in the CBARs following TEI prescribed referencing or citation styles c. Sharing results of the research with an audience through any available platform d. Submitting the action research to the College Supervisor
10. Portfolio	a. Preparing of an electronic portfolio of various field study areas	a. Preparing an electronic portfolio of various teaching-learning experiences and processes. This is to give emphasis on the process rather than output.

Table 1

➤ Challenges in online experiential learning

The teaching profession is examining how a supervised training experience an internship might be used to enrich candidates' abilities and ensure their competence before they practice autonomously. Internship teaching is following the lead of other professions which have found that the internship supplies the opportunity to apply knowledge, make decisions, reflect on performance, and develop competence. In all the efforts to improve the quality of education, there has been very little investment in preparing knowledgeable teachers. Debrah et al. (2021) used semi-structured interviews with student teachers from Ghana and found out that online teaching was deemed ineffective due to the lack of infrastructure, cost of internet data, and poor connectivity. They also argue the importance of student satisfaction as a factor in course design as well as assessment and evaluation measures are important factors in determining the effectiveness of online learning. In Israel, as part of a recruitment drive during the pandemic, future teachers helped practicing ones in lesson design, and actual teaching. These experiences have contributed to their professional development and have shaped their teacher identity. Also, campus personnel provided learner support through tutorials (Donitsa-Schimdt & Ramot, 2020). In the US, KamhiStein et al. (2020) reported that despite some limitations, a mixed-reality software called Mursion was found to be effective in replacing the face-to-face practicum of pre-service teachers. Lastly, Hadar et al. (2020) added that there is a need for curriculum designers to consider social-emotional competencies training in teacher education programs. Aspects such as stress management techniques, mindfulness, crisis management, and the use of digital platforms for education support were deemed important.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter comprises the methods, approaches, and techniques in data gathering. It presents the research design, locale of the study, participant of the study, sampling method, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. In addition, this chapter also includes the ethical consideration and research reflexivity of the study.

A. Research Design

The main point of this study is to uncover the challenges experienced by the pre-service teachers in their online experiential learning courses in the Laboratory School. Thus, the entire research paper utilized a phenomenological study as research design. Specifically, a hermeneutic phenomenological approach because it is focused on subjective experience of individuals or groups.

Creswell (2013) define phenomenology as an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews are conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand experienced the online internship which are the practice teachers. Furthermore, hermeneutic phenomenology is an interpretive process in which researchers makes an interpretation, of the meaning of the lived experiences. Is concerned with the living world or human experience as it is lived and how the researcher obtains thick descriptions about first-hand accounts of experiences of phenomena from the researched and interprets it (Poolathodi & Areekkuzhiyil, 2020). The data is then read, reread, and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the experience of students who took online experiential learning courses in laboratory school.

B. Research Locale

This study was conducted in Eastern Visayas. It is an administrative region in the Philippines called Region 8 that has main two islands which are Samar and Leyte that connects through San Juanico Bridge. The region consists of six provinces which are Leyte, Biliran, Southern Leyte, Western Samar, Eastern Samar and Northern Samar where the participants' 4th year Social Studies majors of Leyte Normal University resides.

C. Participants of the Study

The participants of the study are the 4th year Social Studies majors of Leyte Normal University (LNU) who experienced online experiential learning courses in the academic year 2020-2021 for Field Study and 2021-2022 for Teaching Internship. Specifically, they are nine (9) selected participants from SS41 and SS42. According to Ellis (2016), different textbooks suggest different sized samples for phenomenological research, but in reality, a sample of between 6 and 20 individuals is sufficient.

Purposeful sampling was utilized in selecting the participants of the study. It is a non-probability sampling and commonly used in every qualitative research. According to Business Research Methodology, Purposive sampling (also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling) is a sampling technique in which researcher relies on his or her own judgment when choosing members of population to participate in the study. The researchers will utilize this sampling, considering the time-availability of each pre-service teachers and those who can provide rich and in-depth information from their experience. Moreover, the fact that researchers used their personal judgement to select participants, it is rest assured that the overall findings still holds the experience of a pre-service teachers who experienced online experiential learning courses.

D. Data Collection Method

The researchers employed interview guide which consists of several open-ended questions and topics that need to be covered during the conversation. Interview guide was utilized since the researchers used a one-on-one unstructured in-depth interview strategy to collect data from the research participants. Unstructured interviews allow the researchers to explore an issue in depth with an individual respondent by tailoring their questioning according to how the interview is progressing (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2014).

On the other hand, In-depth interview, according to Showkat (2017) is one of the most efficient means of gathering primary data. Its goal is to elicit in-depth details about an interviewee's experience and viewpoint on a topic. Furthermore, in-depth interviews are useful when you want detailed information about a person's thoughts and experience or want to explore in depth understanding. Interviews are often used to provide context to other data (such as outcome data), offering a more complete picture of what happened and why (Boyce and Neale, 2006). Since this study is focusing on the experience of a student who is an undergraduate internship, the researchers believed that this method of collecting data is suitable.

E. Ethical Consideration

Before gathering the data needed for the study, the researchers created an interview guide questions and letter of consent for the participants. The said letter of consent was sent to the participants through their available social media messaging platforms. The letter covers asking the approval if the participant is willing to be interviewed and become the subject of the study.

After securing the permission, the researchers oriented the participants about the purpose of the study and the process of gathering data, the researchers asked also for the participants' time availability for data gathering. Subsequently, the participants was being informed that they has the right to withdraw at any point for being the subject of the study if there would be an ill at ease on the study. Moreover, permission to record the interview with the participants was asked.

Furthermore, the researchers will explain to participants that any information coming from them will remain confidential and the interview that will be conducting will only use for the study and not for any other purposes. The researchers believed that this was a crucial step for the study that aims to build trustworthiness within the participants and the study itself. Research Reflexivity

In these times of pandemic, where flexible learning has been introduced, each of us, instructors, students, and academic staff, has been profoundly impacted, particularly students. As researchers, the aim is to provide insights that require the majority of HEIs to administer and adapt other flexible learning modes that would initiate learning even without physical encounters, as well as other alternative off-campus learning in accordance with government health and safety standards. The researchers expect that by conducting this study, participants will be able to express their thoughts, feelings and experiences about the implementation of flexible online learning. It's also worth noting that the researchers are students who have dealt with similar issues in a crisis community and are fluent in CHED, which could influence how the data are handled. To avoid being partial and biased, the researchers double-checked data sources, looked for alternate interpretations, discussed findings with colleagues, and double-checked members. Interviews were also transcribed verbatim and submitted back to the subject for accuracy and cross-checking when analyzing the data.

F. Data Analysis

The COVID-19 pandemic has compelled many education institutions and students to move to virtual learning, and this was adjusted to several people who are used to face-to-face classes. In this online learning modality, it became a challenge for all the teachers, education leaders, and students for there are different factors that may interfere with the condition. Specifically, it is more difficult for students to adapt because we knew that every students is not parallel in life. However, the aim of this study is to examine the experiences and challenges of pre-service teachers in their online experiential learning in the Laboratory School. Thus, the researchers anticipate to provide the participants a safe space in expressing their experiences and challenges during their online experiential learning courses.

Hermeneutic phenomenology is considered as interpretive phenomenology which focuses on understanding individual experiences through interpretation. It was emphasized by Creswell that the researcher has an essential part behind for data collection and most specially data interpretation. Having the crucial role of the researchers to

avoid biases in interpreting the results, it is important to consider some steps to avoid biases in interpreting data in hermeneutic phenomenology. The researchers of the study was objective and assured “bracketing” where the researchers was not influence the participants’ understanding of the situation. The conversation from the interview was double-checked, validated with more supported data resources such as observation. The responses of the participants during face-to-face in-depth interview was scrutinized and interpreted only from the experiences and challenges of pre-service teachers during their online experiential learning courses and the experiences of the researches in online learning does not have place on how the data will be treated.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

❖ Overview

The drastic change brought by the pandemic carried challenges considering that experiential learning courses are expected to give students a chance to immerse themselves in the actual classroom experience and emphasized the need for quality teachers for effective learning. This chapter will reveal and elucidate the experiences and challenges of pre-service teachers during online experiential learning in the laboratory school. To provide a thorough information on its experiences and challenges, it was guided with the following questions to explicate:

1. What challenges experienced by the pre-service teachers in their online experiential learning courses in the laboratory school?
2. What adjustments they made in such challenges to complete online experiential learning courses?

A series of questions had been offered to aid in the search for satisfying information to answer the queries. After a series of in-depth interview sessions, textual data gathered from the interview transcripts were subject to coding, thematic analysis, and categorical aggregation. Essential or relevant data patterns that addressed the research problem were found and investigated using thematic analysis. Similarly, themes were employed to convey results in order to interpret and describe the insights from participants.

❖ Result

Thematic analysis had been undertaken on the interview transcripts. The data was analyzed several times in order to uncover repeating patterns of action and consistency as represented in the data. Initial codes were reviewed, defined, and utilized to generate final codes, leading to a definite theme. Using thematic analysis, essential or interesting data patterns that addressed the research problem were identified and examined. Likewise, themes were used to present results to elucidate and describe the participant’s insights.

The following themes and subthemes emerged as repetitive and notable based on the participant's collective experiences, as revealed by the interview transcripts.

1. Teaching-Learning Experience
Subtheme 1: Learning Opportunities
Subtheme 2: Teaching Strategies and Techniques
Subtheme 3: Learning Satisfaction

2. Challenges, Circumstances and Struggle
Subtheme 1: Lack of skills in technology
Subtheme 2: Lack of Communication
Subtheme 3: Not participative students

3. Adjustments of Pre-service teachers
Subtheme 1: Attitude and Behavior
Subtheme 2: Flexibility and Resourcefulness

A. Theme 1: Teaching-Learning Experience

This theme illustrates the various experiences encountered by the pre-service teachers during their Field Study 1 & 2, and Teaching Internship courses through online in the laboratory school. It describes how it worked, how it provides them chances to widen the horizon of their learning. Also, the opportunities they learned to prepare them in their career as professional teacher.

In addition, Teaching-learning experience were identified in Joint CHED-DEPED Memorandum for the New Normal Policies and Guidelines on the Deployment of Pre-service teachers for Field Study and Teaching Internship for AY 2020-2021 that mandated a new normal teaching-learning activities that are expected in the experiential learning courses. This includes class routines, class observation, and preparation of instructional materials, class activities, demonstration teaching, networking and linkages. However, the participants did not mention other activities that recognized in the delivery of experiential learning courses in new normal based from the Joint CHED-DEPED Memorandum but they just uttered what they experienced. Moreover, this main theme underlies with subthemes that will help expound the about Teaching-Learning experience of the participants.

➤ Subtheme 1: Learning Opportunities

Learning is a process that leads to change, which occurs as a result of opportunities for experience and increases the potential for improved performance and future learning (Ambrose et al, 2010). Furthermore, opportunity refers to a scenario in which you have the ability to do something you wish to do and it sometimes a chance for greater success. Thus, the experience of pre-service teachers in the laboratory school does not only relying inside of classroom instruction but also they are given a chance to experience with some linkages inside the university. One participant even mentioned that:

"There are so many learning opportunities that we are able to learn so much from her (FSSTE), we are able to do things like hosting, to be a facilitator, and moderator of an orientation with speakers. Although its online, it gave me an opportunity to be able to practice and be able to discover myself like my teaching skills that needs to improve."

This states the experience encountered by the pre-service teachers during their Experiential Learning courses, they provided opportunities that mold them and even improve their knowledge through first-hand experience. There is an active engagement of pre-service teachers in opportunities to learn through doing, where they can use their theoretical knowledge in a variety of scenarios both inside and outside of the classroom. In addition, other participant pointed out the opportunity they had when they meet the Laboratory School students. The participant indicated that:

“During our Field Study 1, we are more on recitation. While during our Field Study 2, we had an observation to the students in Integrated Laboratory School. With that, we already have an idea with the students we will be having for demonstration teaching.”

This shows the first-hand experience of one of the participants during his Field Study 1 and 2 at the laboratory school, where it emphasized that the classroom observation they conducted through online helped them a lot to familiarize the classroom environment and its students. Classroom observation is one of the teaching-learning process, which is a requisite task in Field Study courses as per CHED Memorandum No. 74 s. 2017; it is the first experiential course which will immerse a future teacher to actual classroom situation and learning environment where direct observation to teaching learning process. Other participants said that:

“During Field Study, aside from having a classroom observation, it was a big help for me specially we focused on important matters which are very essential and relevant to teaching internship, such as making school forms, demo teaching, lesson planning, and it wasn't stressful.”

“During our field study 2 more on practical knowledge, skills development, especially when it comes to creating lesson plan, instructional materials, so more on application of skills”

Wellington (1988) as cited in Mayuga (2016) notes that there are ‘at least six types of activity’ that take place in school ‘that we would probably all class as practical work’: teacher demonstrations; class practicals, with all learners on similar tasks, working in small groups; a circus of ‘experiments’ with small groups engaged in different activities, rotating in a carousel; investigations, organized in one of the above two ways; and problem-solving activities. Based from the responses, it shows that practical knowledge and skills development were employed during their online experiential learning experience. Specifically, they are given aside to create school forms, to have demonstration teaching, making of instructional material and other hands-on skills they need as pre-service teacher. This shows that from the experiences they had, the learning opportunities was vital for them as preparatory in their future endeavor.

➤ *Subtheme 2: Teaching Strategies and Techniques*

In this subtheme, this will show how experiential learning courses being strategized to conduct virtually based from the experience of pre-service teachers' participants. There are a number of different approaches or terms within this broad heading, such as experiential learning. So as to gain conceptual insight as well as practical expertise. Kolb's experiential learning model suggest four stages in this process: Active experimentation, Concrete experience, Reflective observation, and Abstract conceptualization. However, it may still vary from the responses of the participants.

“What happened during our first shift (Internship), it was team teaching, like we are in a group that will teach to students and we are dividing the part of the lesson plan each members.”

(An natabo kasi han amon first shift kay kuan kami team teaching, by group ba kami na magtutudo in tutunga tunga la namon an parts han lesson plan para ig todo pero tanan na students.)

“During our second shift, it was planned already to have an individual teaching but the whole class of our students are being divided and assigned to designated pre-service teacher. Although we only have limited amount of students, the best part was we are able to teach the whole lesson plan”

(an second shift namon nag plapan na adton na individual talaga an amon pagtutudo although an student namon ginturunga la liwat an student, guti la pero good thing gihapon hiya kay at least bug-os na lesson plan ikaw an mag titeach han bug-os na lesson plan.)

“Online teaching internship courses in the laboratory school on the first shift of teaching internship it was individual teaching and each one of us in a group handle 5-7 students only”

“We are more on team teaching wherein we cannot focus individually and can't be able to maximize what we can offer in a classroom setting”

“I remembered hadto nga time, group kami and may specific amount of students la per group, but during the 2nd shift, nagtutudo na kami solo han whole lesson plan”

“I expected that I can teach solo with the students, however, we are group into team teaching.”

From the responses, it shows that during their demonstration teaching in field and teaching internship, they had team teaching in the laboratory school. The team-teaching method is one of the greatest innovations in the teaching sector. It started in the year 1954 in USA and is mainly focus on developing courses and teaching strategies (Reddy, 2022). This kind of strategy is not new anymore in the field of education, however, the practice of team teaching by student teachers during field experiences is still in its infancy; even more so within the context of student teachers' field experiences in secondary education (Bacharach et al., 2010; Stairs et al., 2009). On the other hand, it states from the

responses that after they conducted team teaching, they proceed to individual teaching in the laboratory school. The alternation between individual and team teaching is also mentioned as a condition. The study of Simons & Baeten (2017), this combination best suits teaching reality, as they confirmed the importance of combining team teaching with individual teaching.

➤ *Subtheme 3: Learning Satisfaction*

In this portion, it presents the learning satisfaction by the pre-service teachers during their online experiential learning courses. According to Oliver (1999) as cited in Wu et. al. (2015), learning satisfaction is the impact of the processes which have taken place during the teaching and learning sessions participated by the students. Besides, satisfaction can also be viewed as comparative outcomes between expectancy and perceived service with pleasure or displeasure. With the shift of learning modality to online, likewise to experiential learning courses. It can't assure the fulfillment of the teaching-learning process experience of pre-service teachers. One participant even mentioned that:

"I don't see myself being a teacher, that I will be a competent teacher because I have still lack of experience because I feel that during my second shift in practice was not enough just like my other classmates"

(Dire ko pa nakikita it akon self na magigin teacher, magigin competent na teacher di ko pa talaga nakikita kay feeling ko talaga damo pa it ak pagkukulang, experience na kulang ha akon pero feeling ko kon an akon second shift talaga nakag teach ako sugad an akon iba na classmate nakaka kuan gad)

This provides a stark claim that the experience gained of the pre-service teachers in an online experiential learning cannot give them a guarantee for a complete knowledge and competence they need to have in a field of teaching. In the study of Dunn & Tomlinson (2001), they claim that if students engage with responsive environments and instruction, they will attain results that are more satisfactory. Pre-service teachers' performance expectations may have shifted after the release of COVID-19. Furthermore, during this situation, teacher preparation programs were unable to resolve issues or terminate unsatisfactory placements for their pre-service teachers. Other participant even added that:

"Actually, I am excited on experiential learning, but I feel disappointed because of the pandemic"

(na e-excite talaga ako (on Experiential learning), tas na disappoint kay nag pandemic. Na e-excite pero kinukulba)

The emergence of distance learning brought by the pandemic, it hinder the momentum of the pre-service teachers that makes them unsatisfied knowing that experiential learning courses must integrate in the actual classroom environment.

B. Theme 2: Challenges, Circumstances, and Struggles

It is highly desirable to emphasize the importance of experiential learning in teacher education. During this field activity, pre-service teachers build work relationship with cooperating teachers to plan lessons, prepare projects, assess student knowledge, learn varied teaching styles and effective classroom management, and develop their teaching skills and knowledge in a classroom setting (Abas, 2016). With this, it is necessary to consider the challenges of pre-service teachers as they experienced online experiential learning courses where it is unexpected to happen for them. In this theme, it presents the different challenges faced by the participants based from their responses from the interview. Knowing that it is an undeniable fact that "teacher training" plays an essential role as an effective teacher. Moreover, as these challenges arises one of the major problems that pre-service teachers face is putting theory into practice.

➤ *Subtheme 1: Lack of skills in technology*

Educators today believe in the power of technology and how it positively affects teaching and learning, with that, the use of technology for instruction is gaining widespread acceptance. Teachers must have the knowledge and technical capacity to use technology for instructional delivery in order to effectively employ technology for instruction. However, from the response of the participants, it is mentioned that:

"I'm not into technology. I wasn't prepared at first, like the quarantine started, I don't have enough gadgets but was still be able to manage."

This condition is a challenge of the pre-service teacher who have lack of skills in technology. There is every indication that pre-service teachers not only need pedagogical training, but also training in specific skills. As we live in the 21st century, technology provides important role in teaching-learning process. To delve deep into the problem at hand, knowing the shift of learning modality of experiential learning courses to online, technology is one of the most essential tool for them to attain all the requirements needed. However, this alternation is not parallel with the life condition of different students. The participant getting hard to cope up with the situation he encountered since he don't have enough gadget and he wasn't prepared due to different factors. Other participants even added that:

"I'm not into technology like in using different platforms in online classes, for example, google classroom. I am more confident in messenger and facebook only. In this situation, I always feel nervous and the excitement I had was being diminished."

(Dire ako techy (into technology) na person na makarit mag gamit hin sugad sugad hine na platforms. Ine na mga google kuan (classroom) sugad ito dire talaga ako hito. Okay la ha akon mga kuan messenger, facebook pero sugad iba na nga mga kuan waray talaga iton idea pano gamiton so kinukulba ako dire na ako na e-excite nawara nak excitement.)

“I’m nervous because I’m not competent in technology like using this kind of platform (google meet).”

(Kinulba ako kay dire ako techy na person na makarit mag gamit hin sugad sugad hine na platforms.)

The participants find a challenging situation in using google classroom. As pre-service teacher it is important to be aware in using this kind of platform, as it will serve as your classroom portal in an online experiential learning. Challenges in technology are compounded by the lack of willingness for student teachers to use technology appropriately during teaching practice sessions. Moreover, The issue of pre-service teachers' failure to incorporate technology into classroom instruction is complex. Some of pre-service teachers believed that they lacked the technical skills necessary to deal with technological issues when they encountered them and most of their comments were discouraging.

➤ *Subtheme 2: Lack of efficient communication*

Communication is a functional element of life. It transmits information, ideas, feelings and mutual understanding among people. Everyone has different capabilities to interact with others and there are specific barriers that restrict people's expression. Pre-service teacher use of communication strategies upon receiving immediate feedback or for other queries for announcement about what they will do on their experiential learning courses. In this theme, it shows that communication is one of the challenges faced by the pre-service teacher during their online experiential learning courses. Participant mentioned that:

“Our Supervising Teacher Educator was always delay in giving us instructions during our first shift in internship. Like, the next is day is already our schedule for teaching but the corrections of our lesson plan was given to us midnight in our schedule”

(An amon STE an first shift kay bagat apot-apot ba hiya mag hatag hin instruction. Sugad an amon lesson plan, tomorrow na kami mag titeach tapos an amon lesson plan yana na gab-i pala hiya naghatag han correction, kon ano an am dapat ig improve katapos nag send pagud hiya (Supervising Teacher Educator) mga umagahon)

In the online distance learning, the only way to communicate is through online. From the response, it shows how the participant struggle with the delay of instruction from their Supervising Teacher Educator (STE), which causes to have a limited time of sleep and it affects the quality of output such a in revising their lesson plan that will presented in the next day. Other participant even said that:

“In online, it takes time before our STE reply to our questions.”

(Ha online kasi it takes time before makareply iyo STE adviser.)

As there is no face to face interaction in distance learning courses, lack of communication between students and the teacher has been a problem especially knowing that physical separation can create a sense of isolation. Having this kind of problem needs an immediate solution since it affects the entire quality experience of pre-service teachers, which includes in maximizing what a pre-teacher can offer in the field. Moreover, the success of the performance of pre-service teacher depends upon effective communication of instruction.

➤ *Subtheme 3: Not participative students*

Student engagement is the cornerstone of effective instruction. Schneider, and Shernoff (2003) believe that teachers should focus on student engagement because doing so results in increased student autonomy and appropriate challenges in the classroom. In this theme, it shows that the students of pre-service teachers in the laboratory school was challenged by having not participative students. Participants even responded that:

“In my experience, there are students that I cannot control, and only few are participating in my discussion”

(An akon talaga experience hadton kay mayda mga student na di talaga nasasaway tas pira pira la talaga an naparticipate mayda adton usa usa la an naparticipate)

“Some students are not participative and responsive”

“Since the students are not participating in the discussion, What I am doing is telling them to participate”

(Dire naparticipate an iba, so an iya ginhimo as a teacher in integrated laboratory school ginsisingan mo an imo students)

“The lecture went smooth but I don’t have participative student”

“I really taught it was an easy task but it was a difficult moment for as there were some students who are not responsive and not participative, even if I did all my best still they were not encourage to participate”

From the responses, it shows that they find a hard time in their experience in online experiential learning because of having not participative students. In this situation, pre-service teacher find a hard time in dealing with their students in the laboratory school, despite how prepared the content they are conducting to students. In addition, it an online environment, there is an increase need of engagement because of the border in between teacher and students.

C. Theme 3: Adjustments of Pre-service teachers

➤ Subtheme 1: Attitude and behavior

Attitude refers to a point of view in relation to something or someone, therefore these are personal responses to something according to that person's preference. Behavior is how a person acts or behaves towards himself, especially towards others (Muthoni, 2021). The responses of the participants from the interview mentioned about the adjustments of their attitude and behavior during online experiential learning because of the challenges. During their experiential learning, the pre-service teachers were aware of changes in their attitude and behavior since they were experiencing a different method, which is the new normal learning. The participants even mentioned that:

“I started becoming a night person, sometime brownout during the day, so when it comes to paperwork like making lesson plans and power point presentations, I'm making it gabe ko nala hiya gin hihimo during day time. Also, during day time I will be having a class like teaching students.”

“I am making to do list and take notes”

“During our Field Study, we still to meet despite of having a slow internet connection of the others, we are even having our meeting at midnight just to make sure that everyone has a strong internet connection. I believe we need to sacrifice.”

“They reply immediately when we have concerns and when it comes to our group we actually have meetings, we actually hold meetings and divide out any tasks right away.”

This states that the participants observed that their attitude and behavior, or how they act, must change in order for them to perform their responsibilities as students and pre-service teachers during their online experiential learning. Attitudes are often the result of experience or upbringing, and they can have a powerful influence over behavior (Cherry, 2021). One participant even mentioned that:

“They (High school students) are still cannot be able to adjust their attitude, and its still like elementary and childish”

(Bagan dire pagud hira nakakg adjust han ira attitude kanan elementary like bata-bata pa talaga hira.)

This states that the pre-service teacher observes the students' attitudes in order to develop approaches in managing the students' attitudes, as well as the pre-service teacher's challenges. Furthermore, one participant elucidated that:

“Since DepEd currently offers the brigada pag-basa program (reading program) in our barangay, I volunteered to teach students and its an opportunity for me. I really want to grab opportunities to teach student as my personal practice and experience”

This also includes that this pre-service teacher grabs opportunity to practice herself to experience the field of teaching teacher. The attitude of a person is mainly based on the experience he has acquired during his life and on his observations (Muthoni, 2021). Given the possibility that attitude and behavior are related, a pre-service teacher who gains experience is more likely to be an effective teacher.

➤ Subtheme 2: Flexibility and Resourcefulness

Flexibility, often called differentiation, is important because of the need to respond to different learner abilities, requirements, and interests (Zhandi Theunissen, 2020). In addition, learning should revolve around ourselves since it provides us with strategies and talents to learn about topics we haven't yet discovered or to be flexible and resourceful in our surroundings and even in the situations we encounter, and allowing us to recognize how we will manage and work very hard. Participants even mentioned that:

“At first it was hard for me to adjust but then I realized that I need to cope up with these challenges. What I did was went to place that has a stable internet connection and has a peaceful environment for me to be able to focus to teach”

“I became resourceful because I am always going to the house of my friend or my relatives just to connect wifi or to have stable connection and also I always borrowed their laptop”

This states that in the online experiential learning, pre-service teachers exerted so much effort and poured a lot of sacrifices. They had the mindset to look at what's in front of them and to optimize what they have to work with despite of the challenges they are facing. Being resourceful of the pre-service teachers has an advantage for their training as a future teacher. According to Dunia (2020), being a resourceful teacher is the ability to look at multiple solutions or resources that can cater to the student's needs and learning styles as well. Also, it is a call and duty of a teacher to always never give up in any difficult conditions they might face.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary, conclusions of the study and recommendations for the significant and involved persons and to further research.

A. Summary

This study was conducted for the purpose of uncovering the experiences and challenges of pre-service teachers during their online experiential learning courses at the laboratory school. In interpreting data, thematic method was used, and semi-structured interview was used for data gathering. Interview guide question were used as instrument for collecting data. Purposive sampling were used to get 10 pre-service teachers from 4th year BSED Social Studies of Leyte Normal University to participate the study.

The study findings have been described in line with the statement of problem:

1. What challenges experienced by the pre-service teachers in their online experiential learning courses in the laboratory school?

Based on the findings of the result from the responses of the participants, the researchers find out different challenges faced by the pre-service teachers during their online experiential learning courses in the laboratory school. It was themed as Challenges, Circumstances, and Struggles which includes the subtheme which are the specified challenges encountered by the participants, which are, Lack of skills in technology, Lack of communication, and Not participative students.

2. What adjustments they made in such challenges to complete online experiential learning courses?

Participants had encountered challenges that affects their experience in taking online experiential learning courses in the laboratory school. From the responses of the participants it was themed as Adjustments of Pre-service teachers which includes Attitude and Behavior and Flexibility and Resourcefulness as subtheme. It shows that pre-service teachers had created different ways to surpass all the challenges they undergone.

B. Conclusion

RA No. 7722, undergraduate teacher education in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) throughout the country continuously prepares prospective teachers of basic education sector to accomplish their roles and responsibilities and helps sustain quality education. Experiential learning has been implemented by public and private HEIs that provide teacher education in the country to obtain valuable experience in a real-world learning environment significant comprehension and appreciation for future practicum experiences and the teaching profession. Though such experience learning is unquestionably beneficial in pre-service education, there are certain drawbacks and limiting forces affecting its delivery in terms of quality and impact of a field experience.

COVID-19 pandemic forced a drastic shift in university teacher education, with most face-to-face courses being replaced by online education, which had a significant influence on students. It has been found out that the difficulties encountered by pre-service teachers during online experiential learning in their final year could reveal insights into their early professional steps. Some of these issues are expressed as challenges: most of the participants reveals that they aren't prepared in an online experiential learning courses as they expected to have it in face-to-face approach, they don't have enough gadget or equipment to use and majority of them shared that they are not knowledgeable into technology or they lack of skills in such aspect. Second, majority of them are being challenged of having lack of communication in terms instructions from their STE which causes them to have a delay in making outputs for example in conducting teaching demonstration. Lastly, they having a hard time in making their

teaching-learning process successful because the students that they have are not participative in class. Since they are only facing virtually, pre-service cannot be able to maximize the approaches or methods they will have to gain the attention of the students. Moreover, such difficulties in various aspects may block the enhancement of field experiences like practicum.

As these challenges emerges on their experience in the laboratory school, this includes the adjustments they did just to exceed the necessary requirements for the course. Participants shared that they become flexible and resourceful where they go to place where they can find a good cellular signal just to attend their classes, they asked their friends who have laptops. Aside from that, their attitude also adjust, where they are being reminded by themselves to be motivated and consider all the challenges as a stepping stone for their success in learning. Moreover, some of the participants shared that because of the challenges they encountered, it serves for them as a hindrance to perform well, and the disappointment from what they are expecting in delivering online experiential learning courses in the laboratory school. These also concerned them about the quality of education they obtained from their on-field experience, considering the performance of the university in terms of education in a past year.

C. Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn by the researchers, following recommendation was specified:

- Pre-service teachers must continue to strive learning despite of challenges they faced in their online experiential learning courses.
- Cooperating schools and other involved persons must show their full support for pre-service teachers by establishing a support system in place to address such challenges and difficulties as soon as possible. Such as monitoring the situation of each pre-service teachers.
- Supervising Teacher Educators must ensure an immediate response to the pre-service teachers in providing instructions.
- University must consider the challenges faced by the pre-service teachers to modify the way of delivering Experiential Learning Courses.
- Further studies about experiences and challenges of pre-service teachers in their experiential learning courses.

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